

Operational Excellence

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Assignment Title: Business Value Stream Map and Improvement Identification

Bakery Process Description

Delivery and Storage:

Frozen bakery products are delivered to the store three times a week and stored in a cold store. The correct stock level is managed by a system configured by the user (setting the maximum “shelf capacity”). Based on sales and the number of units of products unsold after baking at the end of the day or withdrawn for other reasons (e.g., damage by the operator, such as dropping the product on the floor) – hereinafter referred to as “W/O” – the system calculates the current demand. It sends the order to the central warehouse.

Baking Planning (“Baking Guidelines”):

Twice a week, on Sundays and Wednesdays, the system generates new Baking Guidelines for the following days, taking into account:

1. Average sales for the last 7 weeks for a given day of the week;
2. Time of the last recorded sale of the product;
3. A buffer ensuring product availability until the store closes;
4. Daily W/O of individual bakery items are NOT considered; however, the overall W/O percentage affects the total buffer size.

Daily Baking:

Each day, 70% of the bakery products specified in the Baking Guidelines are baked before the store opens. This ensures adequate availability in the morning while minimising the risk of excessive waste.

Additional Baking During the Day:

At 1:00 PM, the store employee checks the remaining stock of baked goods. As described in point 2, the Baking Guidelines contain information on the amount of baked goods needed to meet the entire bakery assortment demand. The employee calculates the difference between the demand resulting from the Baking Guidelines and the current stock of baked goods, and bakes the missing amount.

A key drawback of the system is that the last recorded transaction does not necessarily mean the product is unavailable. Some bakery products may sell at different times during the day with varying intensity. Additionally, the system does not consider current sales data or daily turnover.

W/O of Unsold Bakery Products:

Unsold bakery products are classified as W/O. This data is crucial for future orders and assessing the Baking Guidelines' effectiveness. However, it can be distorted because human errors, such as burning bread, are not considered.

Orders for Frozen Bakery Goods:

New orders for frozen bakery goods are generated based on current sales and W/O. This process ensures appropriate stock levels and reduces the risk of shortages but does not prevent over-ordering, which can lead to waste. The system tries to keep stock levels within the maximum shelf capacity.

The products are frozen and have a long shelf life, so they do not require constant rotation. A LIFO (Last In, First Out) strategy is desirable, but at some point, the product expires, leading to losses.

Value Stream Map

I want to point out that when creating this Value Stream Map, I did not have access to up-to-date data on the number of stores handled by the supply chain or other departments or detailed descriptions of the processes in these areas. As a store employee, all the processes and information flow in this analysis are my idea of how the process, which I have tentatively called the “Bakery Process”, works. I want to highlight that many details in this Value Stream Map are based only on my assumptions. Additionally, the data may be completely inaccurate because I have no experience in these areas.

To estimate the FTE for *Purchasing* and *Supply Chain*, I assume that:

- » The *Purchasing* and *Supply Chain* departments serve 50 stores.
- » The ASR system forecasts demand, so the primary role of *Purchasing* and *Supply Chain* is to monitor and make corrections.
- » The *Transport* department handles transportation and is not part of the *Supply Chain*.

1. Purchasing:

Purchasing is responsible for ordering frozen bakery products from suppliers. Their tasks include:

- » Analysing forecasts from ASR (demand forecasts);
- » Contacting suppliers and placing orders;
- » Monitoring deliveries, verifying orders, and handling complaints;
- » Managing a bakery assortment of 20 – 30 products.

Most orders are generated automatically and require human approval.

Based on these assumptions, I estimate the FTE for Purchasing to be 2.

2. Supply Chain:

The Supply Chain transfers deliveries from the central warehouse to stores and generates Baking Guidelines. This includes:

- » Receiving information on stock levels and forecasts;
- » Deciding how much stock each store will receive;
- » Monitoring inventory levels and adjusting delivery plans to prevent shortages or surpluses;
- » Analysing data and creating Baking Guidelines.

Assuming each store receives three deliveries per week, this results in 150 orders per week. Additionally, the Baking Guidelines are generated half automatically. I estimate the Supply Chain FTE to be 5

Figure 1. Value Stream Map for Bakery Process – Current State

Details of the Customers and their Requirements

The customers in this value stream map are retail customers who purchase fresh bakery products directly from the store. They expect fresh bread from the store's bakery to be available throughout the day. To meet customer expectations, fresh bread is baked twice daily, once before the store opens and again at 1:00 PM. After baking, all products are immediately placed on the display shelves to ensure availability throughout the day. The demand for bakery products varies during the day depending on the type of customer and the store's location. The demand and its distribution also change depending on the day of the week. Additional factors include holidays (e.g. Christmas, Bank Holidays), special events (e.g. sports events), and weather (e.g. pleasant weather in the summer season may encourage customers to have afternoon barbecues).

Demands defined of the Suppliers

In the region served by *Supply Chain* and *Purchasing*, which includes 50 stores, the demand for bakery products is determined based on sales data sent daily from stores to the ASR system. The ASR system analyses this data and generates demand forecasts, which are the basis for ordering the appropriate quantities of products from suppliers.

The ordered products are frozen, meaning they have a long shelf life and can be stored in stores for an extended period without any risk of quality loss. As a result, stores have enough space in their backup freezers to maintain stock for about 7-10 days, minimising the risk of shortages. The average number of deliveries to stores is three per week, which helps distribute the delivery load evenly throughout the week.

Due to minor fluctuations in demand, orders remain relatively stable, ensuring the supply chain is not exposed to excessive pressure. Suppliers are responsible for delivering frozen products to the Regional warehouse, from where they are distributed to store cold storage areas, ensuring a continuous replenishment of goods.

Suppliers must maintain the quality of frozen products and provide documentation proving that proper storage temperatures are maintained at all times. The long-term demand forecasts generated by ASR allow suppliers to optimise production without excessive production and storage, ensuring that stores receive products with a long shelf life.

Bakery Process Flowchart

Diagram 1. Bakery process flowchart

Key Process Parameters and Value-Added Analysis

When selecting a process for analysis, I focused on the baking process in the store bakery. From the beginning, I knew it depended on many other organisational processes. However, my main goal was to understand and optimise the stages leading to the preparation of ready-made bakery products, which are ultimately available to store customers.

When creating the VSM, I could not ignore the supporting processes, such as:

- » Purchasing – based on data from ASR, it orders goods from suppliers;
- » Supply Chain – using data from the Regional warehouse, stores, and ASR, it manages the distribution of goods from the Regional warehouse to the Store warehouse and creates Baking Guidelines.
- » Sales – represents the product's sale to the customer and transfers sales information to ASR and Supply Chain.

I believe these processes play an essential role in the overall workflow, but they are not the primary optimisation focus in this analysis. Therefore, I will concentrate on describing critical parameters and identifying Value-Add Activities and Non-Value-Add Activities only for the main bakery processes, which are:

	Critical parameters	Type of Activities
Delivery and storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Delivery frequency: 3 times a week; ▪ Storage conditions: products must be stored at temperatures below -18°C; ▪ Inventory rotation: The current LIFO (Last In, First Out) method can lead to older stocks being held back. 	<p>The process ensures the availability of frozen bakery products for the store's operations, which is classified as Value-Added Activities.</p> <p>However, constantly maintaining inventory at a high level creates unnecessary storage costs. Additionally, inconsistent inventory rotation increases the risk of products being outdated.</p>
Morning bake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Baking volume: The amount of baking depends on the previously generated Baking Guidelines. Morning baking covers 70% of the forecasted daily requirement; ▪ Baking time: 2 – 2.5h; 	<p>This process adds value by providing customers fresh baked goods from when the store opens.</p>

		However, overestimating the batch size can result in overproduction and unnecessary waste.
1:00 PM bake	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Baking volume: The amount of baked goods depends on the previously generated Baking Guidelines. Calculated based on the estimated average sales volume minus the remaining goods baked during the morning baking. ▪ Baking time: 2h; 	<p>The main task of this process is to deliver fresh bread for sale, which is evidence of the Value-Add Activities.</p> <p>However, how the size of this batch is estimated can lead to overproduction.</p>
W/O	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Moment of the day: After the store closes, this process occurs. ▪ Tools: a device is required to log the exact amount of unsold bread into the system. 	<p>This process is intended to log the appropriate amount of unsold bakery products to improve future Baking Guidelines.</p> <p>However, assuming overproduction or underproduction does not provide value.</p>

Identification of Key Problem Areas in the Value Stream

Based on my analysis of the baking process, I have identified two key issues:

1. Inefficient inventory management and product rotation – Physical Problem:

Due to the continuous maintenance of stock at the maximum level and using the LIFO (Last In, First Out) method, this approach is inefficient even with a scheduled rotation process performed once a year. Periodically flagging specific products for rotation and reducing stock levels to a safe but not maximum level would accelerate the rotation process. Managing a smaller quantity of products during rotation is more efficient than handling larger amounts; this procedure will save time and reduce the risk of potential rotation issues.

2. Suboptimal baking forecasting leading to waste (W/O) – Transactional Problem:

The current Baking Guidelines system is primarily based on historical sales data from the last seven weeks and the time of the last recorded sale for a given product. However, the last transaction time does not necessarily indicate that the stock was depleted. Instead, it only reflects when the last customer interested in purchasing that particular bakery item appeared in

the store. The system may mistakenly interpret the lack of sales later as a stock shortage, leading to increased future baking recommendations for that product.

Another issue is that the current system does not account for dynamic factors such as weather conditions, local events, or sudden demand fluctuations on a specific day in a particular store. The system averages sales data based on the last seven weeks, which may contribute to unnecessary overproduction or insufficient baking, especially at 1:00 PM during the second baking. At 1:00 PM, the system does not consider the overall demand, particularly for bakery products on that specific day.

The W/O percentage is a crucial parameter in shaping future Baking Guidelines. However, the current system does not consider the W/O value for individual products. There is a possibility that product A is overproduced, creating a waste level of 50%. At the same time, product B is underproduced, leading to a 0% waste level and a lack of availability. Additionally, failing to distinguish the causes of W/O may result in misinterpreting the data. Products may be logged as waste due to a lack of demand and human errors (e.g., dropping or burning items). The system does not differentiate these causes, making the data less accurate.

Another issue is the lack of information on product availability throughout the day. The system relies on the last recorded sale but does not analyse whether the product was available for the entire day. It is possible that some bakery items were out of stock several hours before closing or even before 1:00 PM, but the system does not account for this in future forecasts.

Description of the current process for identified problems

1. Ineffective inventory management and product rotation – Physical Problem:

Frozen bakery products are delivered to the store three times a week and stored in a cold room. The system is designed to maintain maximum stock levels at all times. Since the LIFO (Last In, First Out) method is used, newly arrived products are placed at the front, and older items remain at the back of the store. Once a year, manual stock rotation is carried out, where employees reorganise products so that older batches are used first. However, this method is inefficient because maintaining maximum stock levels means many products must be reviewed and rotated, making the process time-consuming. Furthermore, the average amount of product stored in the cold room lasts 7-10 days. After the products have been rotated correctly, new deliveries continue to arrive, and the LIFO (Last In, First Out) method is used again, prioritising

the most recently arrived products. Periodically reducing stock levels to a safe, but not maximum, level would allow for faster and more efficient rotation.

Diagram 2. Flowchart of Frozen Bakery Inventory Rotation Process

2. Suboptimal Baking Forecasting – Transaction Problem:

The baking process begins with the generation of Baking Guidelines, which are based on sales data from the past seven weeks. Based on this analysis, the system calculates the expected demand for each bakery product and provides recommendations for baking.

At the beginning of the day, before the store opens, about 70% of the expected daily demand is baked. At 1:00 p.m., the employee checks the status of the remaining bread. Instead of analysing the actual demand in real-time, the system assumes that the last sale of a product is when the product is considered no longer available. Based on this assumption, additional baking is performed according to the guidelines initially generated by the system.

This approach has several drawbacks. The system does not consider dynamic factors such as weather, local events, or current sales trends. Additionally, it fails to consider situations where a product was unavailable earlier in the day, which can lead to underproduction. At the same time,

overproduction can occur because the W/O ratio is treated as an overall percentage rather than being analysed individually for each product.

Diagram 3. Flowchart of Current Baking Forecasting Process

Analysis of Identified Problems and Proposed Improvements: Lean Thinking

Based on the process analysis and the value stream map (VSM), it can be concluded that excessive frozen stock in the warehouse leads to leftover inventory and increases the risk of products expiring. Multiple cost-related factors are linked to transportation during delivery, and a heavy load may be placed on other delivery systems. Therefore, further analysis is needed to identify an appropriate logistics model.

The bakery layout analysis using the 5S tool shows potential for improving the equipment arrangement.

Although the bakery was initially designed to accommodate three ovens, currently only two are in use. Relocating the ovens closer to the workstation could reduce the distance employees need to walk, thereby increasing operational efficiency. However, the position of the finished product racks on the opposite side of the ovens must also be considered. Therefore, further analysis is required to determine the optimal oven placement and ensure the most efficient use of space.

Another significant issue is the space organisation in the cold storage area designated for frozen bakery products. Currently, these products are stored on pallets, which in some cases leads to excessive stock accumulation. Reducing the quantity to an optimal level by introducing shelving in the cold store could improve work ergonomics and reduce the distance employees need to travel when retrieving raw materials for baking. Improving the storage method could also enhance product rotation efficiency and reduce the risk of stock expiring.

Diagram 4. Layout of Bakery Area, Preparation Area, and Freezer Room

Additionally, it would create more space for optimal and better organised storage of other frozen products sold and stored in the same cold store, improving overall space management and streamlining warehouse processes.

Inaccurate historical sales data analysis can lead to overproduction and underproduction, resulting in increased losses or customer dissatisfaction. Implementing advanced sales forecasting algorithms that consider factors such as weather conditions, local events, or sports matches could enable better alignment of production with actual demand. Integrating tools such as Just-in-Time, Kanban, and Kaizen could help establish a comprehensive system for real-time monitoring and optimisation of the baking process.

Additionally, implementing the Poka-Yoke method could enable automatic monitoring of errors in the baking process and the reporting of potential irregularities. This would allow for a quick response and targeted employee training when necessary.

Forecasting sales based on historical data and current sales performance can also improve the efficiency of the baking process. Analysing sales data up to 1:00 p.m. – concerning the size of the morning bake, product availability on shelves, and overall store turnover – would enable more precise planning of additional baking during the second half of the day. Additionally, factoring in weather conditions and local events could significantly impact projected demand.

A more accurate classification of losses into “final surplus” and “other causes” would allow for better identification of waste sources and implementing targeted actions to reduce losses. Data on the availability of individual products throughout the day would also support more precise demand forecasting and help avoid situations where customers cannot find their desired baked goods on the shelves.

Implementing the above improvements could enhance the bakery’s operational efficiency, reduce costs, and improve product availability for customers, ultimately increasing consumer satisfaction and supporting better organisation of team workflow.

Analysis of Identified Problems and Proposed Improvements: Six Sigma

Based on my analysis of the Bakery process above, the key issues I have identified are:

1. **Inefficient management of frozen baked goods inventory and product rotation:** Poor inventory management leads to suboptimal ordering, resulting in losses due to product expiration, and thus generating financial waste.

2. **Losses resulting from inaccurate sales forecasting:** Inaccurate forecasts lead to overproduction, causing resource waste. On the other hand, there are periods when demand for certain products is higher than expected, making them unavailable, which may result in customer dissatisfaction and loss of loyalty.

The proposed improvements aim to develop a system that enables accurate monitoring and analysis of loss-related causes. Based on the collected data, such a system would support identifying and understanding waste sources, improve the sales forecasting process, and ultimately lead to optimised baking guidelines. Additionally, reducing variability would enable the design of a personalised and efficient layout for frozen inventory, helping to maintain optimal stock levels and minimise expiration-related losses, for example, by implementing a more effective stock rotation system.

To achieve this, a system will be required to collect both quantitative and qualitative data to understand the scale of the problem and establish a baseline for future improvements. Currently, the system records loss percentage, frozen stock levels, and the percentage deviation between planned and actual baking. However, to fully understand the situation, the following data should also be collected:

- » Accurate identification of loss causes (e.g. overproduction, expired items in the cold store, human error such as dropped products, or products abandoned by customers).
- » A tool that allows operational employees to report out-of-stock events, providing the system responsible for creating baking guidelines with real-time insights into product availability, particularly at 1:00 p.m. for afternoon baking and at the end of the day. This would allow better, faster adjustments of baking forecasts based on concrete data.

A complete analysis could be conducted using this data. However, the current system collects only fragmented and disconnected data, making it difficult to understand the root causes of errors. As a result, the baking guidelines system is based on incomplete information, preventing operational staff and the team responsible for developing the guidelines from optimally adjusting the baking volume.

To ensure that I was not fixating solely on the issues I initially identified and to avoid overlooking other equally essential root causes of waste, I asked my colleagues who work directly with this process to participate in a brainstorming session. As a result, the following extended list of waste contributors was developed:

1. Poorly estimated baking guidelines, leading to underestimation of demand.
2. Poorly estimated baking guidelines, leading to overproduction.
3. Unnecessary consumption of BRP (Bakery Responsible Person) time and energy due to overproduction.

4. Waste due to a suboptimal size of frozen stock.
5. Waste due to excessive frozen stock that was not appropriately rotated and expired before use.
6. Waste due to product unavailability caused by insufficient frozen stock, resulting from supplier or transport issues.
7. Waste due to employee errors, such as incorrect scanning of products at the checkout, destruction of a batch during production (e.g. dropping semi-finished products on the floor), miscounting during baking based on baking guidelines, or errors in demand estimation when preparing for afternoon baking.
8. Waste due to damaged equipment (e.g. oven).
9. Waste due to power outage.
10. Products that are broken or of low quality are written off (W/O). Bread cut by a customer and left behind, half-eaten products left on the shop floor, or products missing on the shelf because they are sold out and not yet defrosted or baked.

The identified issues can be visualised using an Ishikawa (cause-and-effect) diagram:

Diagram 5. Ishikawa Diagram of Waste in the Bakery Process

The above diagram and categorising losses into leading potential causes allow for a more detailed analysis of each identified issue. This approach makes it possible to more precisely determine which factors significantly impact losses and to what extent.

However, as previously noted, the key to such analysis lies in the implementation of more accurate tools that can support this process. Only with access to more precise and comprehensive data will it be possible to conduct more advanced analyses, such as those based on statistical methods like Six Sigma, to enhance bakery operations further.

Ultimately, I believe that implementing an effective data management and demand forecasting system can significantly reduce waste, improve customer service quality, and optimise costs – factors that, in the current situation, are essentially the root cause of the process inefficiencies.

Application of the TRIZ Method in the Analysis of Bakery Process Problems

The TRIZ method is based on the idea that most problems organisations face have already been solved.

In the case of the bakery process being analysed, customer expectations – and therefore assumptions – are that fresh products should be available in the bakery even in the evening. This can lead to overproduction and cause losses.

One possible solution could be inspired by practices used by competing retail chains, such as Tesco. There, bread is available fresh until the afternoon, and in the evening, before the store closes, products are discounted. This approach helps reduce losses and encourages customers to shop at the end of the day.

Decision-makers could think about using a similar strategy. Introducing a system of dynamic discounts on fresh bread at the end of the day would help balance product availability with minimising losses.

Improved Process Flowchart

Based on the process analysis and the identified problems, I believe a flowchart diagram is the most suitable tool to present the proposed improvements. A clear visualisation will help better understand the new process, allowing for a clearer illustration of changes in inventory management and baking forecasting.

Diagram 6. Flowchart of Improved Bakery Process